

Deliverable D3.3.2

D3.3.2 COVID-19 Data Portal

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1. Executive Summary

The BY-COVID project is one of the Horizon Europe projects that has supported the operation and enhancements of the European COVID-19 Data Portal¹, a critical resource that provides access to open literature and data on both the SARS-CoV-2 virus and the COVID-19 disease. As of June 2024, the portal contains ca. 15 million viral sequences and more than one million open scientific articles related to SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19.

BY-COVID Work Package 3 is focused on services for the discovery and integration of COVID-19 data by delivering a flexible, tiered metadata discovery system across different domains, metadata standards, and maturity/robustness levels of data sources. This enables the linking of FAIR data and metadata on SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19, and crucially, on other related viruses and diseases, and on socio-economic factors and consequences, integrating across research fields, from omics, clinical, and epidemiological research, to social sciences and humanities, thereby improving preparedness for future potential emergent disease or pandemic scenarios.

Based on the metadata model developed in D3.1, WP3 has implemented the infrastructure to support the three-tiered discoverability concept in the COVID-19 Data Portal as described in D3.2. Deliverable D3.3.1 (September 2023) provided a status report of the Portal. The present report describes progress since D3.3.1 and addresses new resources, usage indicators, credit attribution, and the transition to the new Pathogens Portal.

¹ COVID-19 Data Portal: <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/> [accessed 29/05/2024]

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached, or the deliverable has contributed to, the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result Number and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Enable storage, sharing, access, analysis and processing of research data and other digital research objects from outbreak research	1. A research data management practice in European research infrastructures practice that drives discovery, access and reuse of outbreak data and directly links experimental data from HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EMERGENCY-02 transnational access projects into the COVID-19 Data Portal.	Yes
	2. Workflows and processing pipelines that integrate transparent quality management and provenance and are openly shared.	Yes
	3. Research infrastructures on-target training so that users can exploit the platform	No
	4. Engagement so that stakeholders (RI, national centres, policy makers, intergovernmental organisations, funders and end-users) incorporate FAIR and open data in infectious disease guidelines and forward planning.	Yes
Objective 2 Mobilise and expose viral and human infectious disease data from national centres	1. A comprehensive registry of available data with established procedures to collate data governance models, metadata descriptions and access mechanisms in a pandemic scenario.	Yes
	2. Mechanisms for the initial discovery across data sources based on available metadata at the reference collection.	Yes
	3. Demonstrated transnational linking of real-world data from national surveillance, healthcare, registries and social science data that allow the assessment of variants to serve the research needs of epidemiology and public health.	Yes
	4. Demonstrated assessment of emerging SARS-CoV-2 variants against data generated in the on-going European VACCELERATE clinical trials project to investigate vaccine efficacy.	No
Objective 3	1. A platform that links normative pathogen genomes and variant representations to research cohorts and mechanistic studies to understand the biomolecular determinants of	Yes

<p>Link FAIR data and metadata on SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19</p>	<p>variant response on patient susceptibility, and disease pathways.</p> <p>2. An open and extensible metadata framework adopted cross-domain that supports comprehensive indexing of the infectious disease resources based on mappings across resources and research domains.</p> <p>3. A provenance framework for researchers and policy-makers that enables trust in results and credit to data submitters, workflow contributors and participant resources.</p>	<p>Yes</p> <p>Yes</p>
<p>Objective 4 Develop digital tools and data analytics for pandemic and outbreak preparedness...</p>	<p>1. Broad uptake of viral <i>Data Hubs</i> across Europe deliver an order-of-magnitude increase in open viral variant detection and sharing.</p> <p>2. Infrastructure and quality workflows mobilised and shared to produce open, normative variant data that is incorporated into national and regional data systems and decision making.</p>	<p>No</p> <p>No</p>
<p>Objective 5 Contribute to the Horizon Europe European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership and European Health Data Space (EHDS)</p>	<p>1. Guidelines and procedures for FAIR data management and access will be established, building on work of other guideline producing consortia such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH), the 1Mio Genomes Initiative (1MG) and the Beyond One Million Genomes project (B1MG).</p> <p>2. Services, software, protocols, guidelines and other research objects that are openly accessible for reuse by the EOSC Association and the community at large as a foundation for European preparedness for infectious diseases, leveraging developments in EOSC-Life, SSHOC, EOSC-Future, EGI-ACE and other EOSC projects.</p> <p>3. Alignment (both policy and implementation routes) will have been achieved between the data governance strategies for routinely collected health data in the EHDS initiative, including the TEHDAS Joint Action and future EHDS Pilot Actions.</p> <p>4. To empower national centres to build capacity and train platform users and data providers (e.g., from life, social or health sciences), and with experts from across partner institutions collaborating to create training materials for the identified gaps, and to exchange experiences and knowledge.</p>	<p>Yes</p> <p>Yes</p> <p>No</p> <p>Yes</p>

3. Introduction

The BeYond-COVID (BY-COVID) project is one of the Horizon Europe projects that has supported the operation and enhancements of the European COVID-19 Data Portal², a critical resource that provides access to literature and data on both the SARS-CoV-2 virus and the COVID-19 disease. As of June 2024, the portal contains ca. 15 million viral sequences and more than one million open scientific articles related to SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19.

BY-COVID aims to provide comprehensive open data on SARS-CoV-2, COVID-19, and other viruses and infectious diseases, across scientific, medical, public health and policy domains. The project mobilises existing data resources (i.e catalogues) and marshals the resources for research, connects and exposes the data and resources via the COVID-19 Data Portal, and drives use and analysis by connecting workflows, national portals and analysis environments. The 3-year project brings together 53 partners from 19 countries.

This deliverable is part of BY-COVID Work Package 3 that is focused on services for the discovery, integration and citation of COVID-19 data by delivering a flexible, tiered metadata discovery system across different domains, metadata standards, and maturity/robustness levels of data sources. This enables the linking of FAIR [1] data and metadata on SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19, on other related viruses and diseases, and on socio-economic consequences, across research fields, from omics, clinical, and epidemiological research, to social sciences and humanities.

Our inter-domain metadata mapping (Task 3.1, D3.1 Metadata standards³) supports (meta-)data discovery, access, and analysis across fields from molecular biology to social sciences. The harmonised metadata is discoverable through the central index (Task 3.2, D3.2 Implementation of cloud-based, high performance, scalable indexing system⁴) and web portal (Task 3.3, D3.1.1 COVID-19 Data Portal⁵), but also openly accessible for third party applications through web services. We have continuously improved the COVID-19 Data Portal in terms of technology and content. In particular, we have added more than 160

² COVID-19 Data Portal: <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/>

³ Hermjakob H, Kleemola M, Moilanen K, Sansone S-A, Lister A, David R, Panagiotopoulou M, Ohmann C, Bellen J, Lischke J, Juty N & Soiland-Reyes S. (2022). BY-COVID - D3.1 - Metadata standards. Documentation on metadata standards for inclusion of resources in data portal (V1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6885016>

⁴ Hermjakob H, Kleemola M, Moilanen K, Tuominen M, Sansone S-A, Lister A, David R, Panagiotopoulou M, Ohmann C, Belien J, Lischke J, Juty N & Soiland-Reyes S. (2022). BY-COVID D3.2: Implementation of cloud-based, high performance, scalable indexing system. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7129553>

⁵ Hermjakob, H., Kleemola, M., Ventouratou, M., Lister, A., Sansone, S.-A., David, R., Lischke, J., Navest, R., Belien, J., Juty, N., Soiland-Reyes, S., & Goble, C. (2023). BY-COVID D3.3.1: COVID-19 Data Portal. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8386828>

related resources⁶ based on the FAIRsharing workflow in collaboration with WP2, and indexed five new resources. Here, we describe the developments since September 2023, the current status of the COVID-19 Data Portal, sustainability, credit attribution, and the transition to the new Pathogens Portal⁷.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Discoverability: EBI Search and three-tiered approach

The discoverability concept of the COVID-19 Data Portal is based on the EBI Search system and a three-tiered indexing concept. These are described in detail in D3.2, so here we provide only a short summary. Since D3.3.1, the indexing and portal infrastructure have remained in stable production mode.

EBI Search [2] is a cloud-based, high performance, scalable text search engine that provides easy and uniform access to the biological data resources hosted at the European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI). EBI Search, based on Apache Lucene, provides inter-domain navigation via a network of cross-references. It can be accessed over the web or programmatically using the RESTful Web Services interface. This allows its search and retrieval capabilities to be exploited in workflows and analytical pipelines. The API-based query interface⁸ is available both within and outside EMBL-EBI, and can be used to develop website-specific search/results pages.

Exposing and effectively connecting and linking different data types requires indexing based on cross-mapped metadata, as described in D3.1. Indexing and incorporation of metadata into the COVID-19 Data Portal proceeds via a flexible, tiered system for metadata integration (Table 1). As described for the Infectious Diseases Toolkit (IDTk) in D3.3.1, external resources over the course of the project can migrate from tier 3 upwards, as resources for the detailed metadata converge upon data harmonisation, and improved technical indexing becomes available.

Table 1. Three-Tiered Indexing Concept

Tier 1	Deepest indexing available, capturing granular, record level identifiers and metadata, support for interoperability use cases.	Aim: Key resources migrate from Tier 3 to Tier 1
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⁶ COVID-19 Data Portal Related resources: <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/related-resources> [accessed 29/05/2024]

⁷ Pathogens Portal: <https://www.pathogensportal.org/> [accessed 2/06/2024]

⁸ EBI Search API: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ebisearch/apidoc.ebi> [accessed 29/05/2024]

Tier 2	Coarse-grained metadata and attributes, focus on record level discoverability.	over project duration. ↑
Tier 3	Focus on resource level discoverability.	

4.2 BY-COVID FAIRsharing resource collection

FAIRsharing⁹ is a manually curated, informative and educational resource that maps the landscape of community-developed standards, databases (repositories and knowledge bases) and policies across disciplines. As of May 2024, it contains 1755 standards, 2122 databases and 265 policies, citable via DOI. FAIRsharing complements the COVID-19 Data Portal by acting as a catalogue of data sources, describing their characteristics including access terms and protocols, and the standards used at the source to represent the data. Resource metadata (Tier 3) is captured in FAIRsharing records and selectively imported to the COVID-19 Data Portal through the API.

The FAIRsharing BY-COVID Collection¹⁰ is a catalogue and knowledge graph¹¹ of BY-COVID data sources and their characteristics, including access terms, protocols and standards used to represent the data and metadata. The Collection currently contains 72 resources, which are 20 data sources (Table 2) and 52 standards, and was developed in collaboration between WP2 and WP3, by BY-COVID members from social science and humanities, health and clinical data, image, genomic and phenotypic data and chemical biology.

Table 2. Resource component of the BY-COVID FAIRsharing resource collection (as of 30 May 2024)¹²

Domain	Resource and record in FAIRsharing	Type of data
Clinical and health	Health Data Research Innovation Gateway; https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.nh1DmP	UK health datasets
	European Health Information Portal (HIP); https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.8690f1	European health information
	ECRIN Clinical Research Metadata Repository; https://fairsharing.org/3067 (awaiting DOI)	Clinical studies, trial registrations, results summaries, journal articles, protocols (global scope)

⁹ FAIRsharing: <https://fairsharing.org/> [accessed 30/05/2024]

¹⁰ BY-COVID Data Resources in FAIRsharing: <https://fairsharing.org/3773> [accessed 30/05/2024]

¹¹ BY-COVID knowledge graph representation in FAIRsharing: <https://fairsharing.org/graph/3773> [accessed 2/6/2024]

¹² The current status of the BY-COVID FAIRsharing resource collection: <https://fairsharing.org/3773>

	BBMRI-ERIC Directory; https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.q9VUYM	Aggregate information about biobanks across Europe
	Dutch National COVID-19 clinical data dashboard; https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.71bf06	Clinical data dashboard for the exploration and reuse of clinical data from Dutch university medical centres
	COVID-19 Data Portal; https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.f3b7a9	COVID-19 datasets and tools including SARS-CoV-2 sequence data
	Dutch National COVID-19 metadata portal; https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.527321	Dutch national COVID-19 metadata portal which describes health datasets
Genotypic and phenotypic	The European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA); https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.mya1ff	Personally identifiable genetic, phenotypic, and clinical data
	European Mouse Mutant Archive (EMMA); https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.g2fjt2	Mutant mice strains essential for basic biomedical research provided by INFRAFRONTIER
Social sciences and humanities	EUI COVID-19 social sciences and humanities (SSH) Data Portal; https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.97367f	COVID-19-related research in the social sciences and humanities
	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA) Data Catalogue; https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.a12316	European social science data
	European Social Survey (ESS) Data Portal; https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.a03ea9	European cross-national survey data measuring the attitudes, beliefs and behaviour patterns of diverse populations in more than thirty nations
	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE) Research Data Center; https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.a9b7aa	European survey data on the effects of health, social, economic and environmental policies over the life-course of European citizens and beyond
	Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations (ODISSEI) Portal; https://fairsharing.org/4841 (awaiting DOI)	Metadata from most data collections relevant to the social science community in the Netherlands

Images	Electron Microscopy Public Image Archive (EMPIAR); https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.dff3ef	Raw images underpinning 3D cryo-EM maps and tomograms
	Electron Microscopy Data Bank (EMDB); https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.651n9j	Electron microscopy density maps of macromolecular complexes and subcellular structures
	Image Data Resource (IDR); https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.6wf1zw	Image data from genetic, RNAi, chemical, localisation and geographic high content screens, super-resolution microscopy and digital pathology
	Biolmage Archive; https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.x38D2k	Biological images that are useful to life-science researchers
Chemical Biology	ChEMBL; https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.m3jtpg	Chemical, bioactivity and genomic data to aid the translation of genomic information into effective new drugs
	European Chemical Biology Database (ECBD); https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.c90baa	Experimental results from biological screening programs
	COVID 19-NMR; https://fairsharing.org/4850 (awaiting DOI)	RNA and protein structural data for SARS-CoV-2 as well as other viruses

In the FAIRsharing BY-COVID Collection individuals and organisations behind these data sources and standards are identified and credited via use of ORCID and ROR. In addition to the BY-COVID Collection, FAIRsharing provides a wider collection of 99 resources potentially relevant to COVID-19 research¹³. As described in D3.2, we have established a workflow to integrate the resources from both collections into the COVID-19 Data Portal section “Related Resources” (Tier 3)¹⁴, which now contains 162 resources. The ultimate scope of the FAIRsharing BY-COVID Collection is also to ‘push’ the descriptions of the data

¹³ Wider collection of COVID-19 resources is maintained by the FAIRsharing team and is focused on patient response, clinical trials, virology studies or other related areas. The databases in the collection contain COVID-19 related datasets. <https://fairsharing.org/3538> [accessed 30/05/2024]

¹⁴ COVID-19 Data Portal Related resources <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/related-resources> [accessed 29/05/2024]

sources and their standards into the OpenAIRE Research Graph¹⁵, enabling it to be part of the EOSC ecosystem, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. FAIRsharing BY-COVID Collection in the ecosystem.

4.3 New Data Sources in the Portal

WorkflowHub

The WorkflowHub¹⁶ is a registry for describing, sharing and publishing scientific computational workflows. It aims to facilitate discovery and re-use of workflows in an accessible and interoperable way. This is achieved through extensive use of open standards and tools, including CWL, RO-Crate, Bioschemas and GA4GH's TRS API, in accordance with the FAIR principles. WP4 developed a BY-COVID Guide to using WorkflowHub¹⁷ which includes guidance on tagging workflows with appropriate metadata. Workflows are recommended to be tagged by “BY-COVID” and “Covid-19” by the submitters.

To facilitate discovery of Covid-19-related workflows, we accessed the WorkflowHub API at [https://workflowhub.eu/workflows.json?filter\[tag\]=covid-19](https://workflowhub.eu/workflows.json?filter[tag]=covid-19) and developed a parser for the RO-Crate Metadata JSON¹⁸ format to retrieve relevant metadata entries and index them in the Covid-19 data portal. These are updated daily by taking advantage of the WorkflowHub

¹⁵ OpenAIRE Graph: <https://graph.openaire.eu/> [accessed 04/06/2024]

¹⁶ WorkflowHub: <https://workflowhub.eu/> [accessed 2/6/2024]

¹⁷ The BY-COVID Guide to using WorkflowHub: <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.sop.10.1> [accessed 25/06/2024]

¹⁸ ROCrate: <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/> [accessed 3/6/2024]

APIs feature to retrieve recently updated workflows¹⁹. As of 2/6/2024, 44 workflows are indexed.

ECRIN's Clinical Research Metadata Repository (crMDR)

ECRIN, the European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network, facilitates multinational clinical research, through the provision of advice and services for the set-up and management of investigator or SME led clinical studies in Europe. As part of its tool offer, ECRIN has developed and operates the clinical research metadata repository (crMDR), a searchable database of all registered clinical studies, together with links to the source registry pages, the results entries or results summary files, linked papers, protocols, data collection forms and other related documents, and datasets²⁰.

In collaboration with the ECRIN team, the COVID-19 Data Portal parses data provided via a REST endpoint specifically developed to export data in the recommended XML format. The endpoint already filters the crMDR data to only show COVID-19 related entries. The endpoint can be found at <https://crmdr.ecrin.org/api/Study/OmicsDIdata/COVID/1/10>²¹. As of 03/06/2024, 17,239 crMDR entries are available in the COVID-19 Data Portal.

As part of Task 3.1, ECRIN and CESSDA investigated whether metadata schemas and vocabularies used for discovering scientific studies and resources in the social sciences and in clinical research are similar enough to allow information from different source disciplines to be easily retrieved and presented together. As output of this task, a detailed crosswalk between the CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC)²² Metadata Profile and the ECRIN clinical research Metadata Schema²³ has been published in Zenodo²⁴. In addition, a full report of the activity is provided in the form of an open access publication in Open Research Europe [3].

Swedish Pathogens Portal

Since its inception, the COVID-19 Data Portal maintained close linkage with national COVID-19 portals, see e.g. D3.3.1, Figure 3. As the focus of the research community shifted from COVID-19 to general pandemic preparedness, the portals developed strategies to ensure that the emerging needs of the research community could continue to be met. EMBL-EBI developed the Pathogens Portal as a sibling to the COVID-19 portal. Both share the same concepts and infrastructure, but are two distinct web sites. Sweden has chosen a

¹⁹ For example:

[https://workflowhub.eu/workflows.json?filter\[tag\]=covid-19&filter\[updated_at\]=PT24H](https://workflowhub.eu/workflows.json?filter[tag]=covid-19&filter[updated_at]=PT24H)

²⁰ ECRIN Clinical Research Metadata Repository <https://newmdr.ecrin.org/> [accessed 2/6/2024]

²¹ The numbers at the end of the URL are for pagination, where the first is the index of the first entry to retrieve and the second is the number of entries (starting from that first one) to retrieve.

²² CESSDA Data Catalogue: <https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/> [accessed 04/06/2024]

²³ <https://zenodo.org/records/8368709>

²⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/8129621> [accessed 1/7/2024]

different approach, converting its COVID-19 portal to the national Pathogens Portal²⁵. During this transition, the scope of the portal was expanded to include a broad range of pathogens, including SARS-COV-2, and general pandemic topics, such as antibiotic resistance. As of June 2024, the content includes data on SARS-CoV-2, influenza, antibiotic resistance, and multiple enteric viruses.

The Swedish team has been working closely with the EMBL-EBI team to enhance linkage between the European COVID-19 Data Portal, the European Pathogens Portal, and national portals. To this end, the Swedish team has created a metadata file describing the data dashboards of the Swedish Pathogens Portal. The dashboards include data, dynamic data visualisations, and information about the research project and how to access and cite the data. The metadata are indexed and included in the European COVID-19 and Pathogens Portals, depending on whether the dashboard relates to COVID-19 or other topics related to pandemic preparedness, respectively (see figure 2). Crucially, the use of the BY-COVID metadata format defined early in the project will allow for future easy addition of fine-grained metadata content from national portals, to both the European COVID-19 Data Portal and the European Pathogens Portal, as well as an easy distinction between COVID-19 and wider pathogen preparedness data.

National portals
National data portals related to COVID-19

Search [] Search []
Examples: sweden ... Advanced search []

Showing 15 of 18 in All > National portals > Sweden

Data types [] [] [] [] Edit table view []

All
National portals (18)
Sweden (18)

Country
 Sweden (18)

Pathogen type
 SARS-CoV-2 (15)
 Influenza (1)
 Enteric viruses (1)

Data type
 Wastewater (8)
 Case_number (2)
 Wasterwater (1)

Dataset name
Antibody testing for SARS-CoV-2 at SciLifeLab, Sweden
Data from COVID Symptom Study Sweden
Swedish COVID-19 publication database
Data from the CRUSH Covid Uppsala study
COVID-19 test statistics from the National Pandemic Centre
Data on the occurrence of post COVID-19 condition (long COVID) in Sweden
Data from register-based large-scale national population study to monitor COVID-19 vaccination effectiveness and safety (RECOVAC)
SARS-CoV-2 whole genome sequencing
Vaccine administration: COVID-19
SARS-CoV-2 quantification in wastewater (Gothenburg University)

Figure 2. National Portals dataset view in the COVID-19 portal.

²⁵ Swedish Pathogens Portal: <https://www.pathogens.se/> [accessed 2/6/2024]

Dutch National COVID-19 metadata portal

The Dutch National COVID-19 metadata "search and request" portal²⁶ allows exploration and reuse of a variety of data acquired in the Netherlands. This includes observational (clinical/health) data from COVID-19 observational projects funded by ZonMw, clinical data from Dutch university medical centres, environmental data and social science and humanities data. The dashboard provides researchers with a clear overview of available datasets, allowing them to search for specific data and simplifying access to such data where the necessary ethical and legal conditions have been met. Re-using the tools developed for the European Health Information Portal²⁷, we have added the relevant records of the Dutch National COVID-19 metadata portal to the COVID-19 Data Portal, benefitting from the DCAT standard and FAIR Data Point specifications to minimise development time. Similarly to the European Health Information Portal, we parse the DCAT datasets to make them discoverable via the COVID-19 Data Portal. In the reporting period, the Dutch National COVID-19 metadata portal has been moved from a preliminary development location to its current production location²⁸, and procedures have been updated accordingly. Data is checked daily for updated entries by consulting the "metadataModified" property of the root MetadataService entry of the Dutch National COVID-19 metadata portal. As of 05/06/2023, there are 163 entries available. The Dutch National COVID-19 data is presented as a facet of Research Infrastructures metadata in COVID-19 Data Portal at

<https://covid19dataportal.org/search/research-infrastructures>.

IDDO

The Infectious Diseases Data Observatory (IDDO) brings together members of the global infectious disease community across the research, humanitarian, and policymaker sectors, to collaborate in the generation, analysis and application of data, with the ultimate aim of improving outcomes for patients. IDDO's coordinating office is based in the Centre for Tropical Medicine and Global Health at the University of Oxford.

As part of its activities, IDDO maintains disease-specific data platforms for a number of infectious diseases, among them SARS-COV-2. These data platforms provide curated catalogues of clinical studies²⁹. In early 2024, IDDO, represented by the University of Oxford, joined the BY-COVID consortium, with the aim of curating and providing metadata for clinical studies across the range of its target diseases, including SARS-COV-2. As of June

²⁶ Health-RI COVID-19 initiatives: <https://covid19initiatives.health-ri.nl/> [accessed 19/09/2023]

²⁷ <https://www.healthinformationportal.eu/>

²⁸ <https://fdp.healthdata.nl>

²⁹ IDDO Covid-19 data platform page: <https://www.iddo.org/covid-19> [accessed 2/6/2024]

2024, we are defining the metadata transfer and update strategy with the IDDO team, expecting to integrate a large set of study metadata by the end of the BY-COVID project.

4.4 Website Development

All new metadata resources are discoverable through the COVID-19 Data Portal global search. The addition of the new resources, as well as requests from project partners and users, resulted in regular website updates. The ECRIN Clinical Research Metadata Repository data has been added to the “Research Infrastructures” section, greatly increasing the searchable content (Figure 3). Data from the Swedish Pathogens Portal is now discoverable via the global search results, and linked directly from the “National Data Portals” page.

The screenshot shows the COVID-19 Data Portal interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for 'About', 'Tools', 'FAQ', 'Related Resources', 'Bulk Downloads', and 'Submit Data'. Below this is a secondary menu with categories like 'Viral sequences', 'Host sequences', 'Expression', 'Proteins', 'Networks', 'Cohorts', and 'More'. The main content area features a search bar with the text 'Research infrastructures' and a sub-header 'Accelerating research through data sharing'. A search button is visible. Below the search bar, there are examples and an 'Advanced search' link. The search results section shows 'Showing 12 of 17,371 in All > Research infrastructures'. On the left, there is a 'Data types' sidebar with a list of categories: 'All', 'Research infrastructures (17,371)', 'European Health Information Portal (32)', 'EU-OPENSREEN (5)', 'Dutch National COVID-19 metadata portal (95)', and 'ECRIN's Clinical Research Metadata Repository (17,239)'. The 'ECRIN's Clinical Research Metadata Repository' entry is highlighted with a red box. The main results list includes:

- European Health Information Portal** 32 results
- COSMO-Spain**
 - Cross references: [Ontology Lookup Service \(OLS\) \(13\)](#)
 - Source: phiri
- COVID-19 Belgian Database**
 - Cross references: [Ontology Lookup Service \(OLS\) \(8\)](#)
 - Source: phiri
- Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on drug use and addictions**
 - Cross references: [Ontology Lookup Service \(OLS\) \(3\)](#)
 - Source: phiri

Figure 3. Research Infrastructures including ECRIN metadata entries in the COVID Portal

Deep highlighting functionality has been implemented, allowing users to click through to a result with search terms appearing as highlighted text (on compatible browsers) (Figure 4). This improves user experience, enabling them to see their search terms in context in the final search result.

COVID-19 Data Portal

Search results for: SARS-COV2 [X]

Showing 6 of 26 in All > Expression

Protein expression experiments 23 results

SARS-CoV2 manipulates multiple NK ligands and inhibits NK activation, but this can be overcome by ADNKA, which is strongly activated by non-Spike targeting antibodies

SARS-CoV2 is recognised the antagonise the interferon response, and functioning interferon responses are critical in determining the severity of disease. However, whether the virus antagonises ... epithelial cells to investigate viral manipulation of cell surface ligands, revealing that SARS-CoV2 does ...

Source: pride

PRIDE
PRoteomics IDentifications Database

Home Resources Tools Help License About Contact

Project PXD025000

Sars-cov-2 Covid-19

Summary Identification Results

Title
SARS-CoV2 manipulates multiple NK ligands and inhibits NK activation, but this can be overcome by ADNKA, which is strongly activated by non-Spike targeting antibodies

Description
SARS-CoV2 is recognised the antagonise the interferon response, and functioning interferon responses are critical in determining the severity of disease. However, whether the virus antagonises cellular immunity has not been determined. We used quantitative plasma membrane proteomics in lung epithelial cells to investigate viral manipulation of cell surface ligands, revealing that SARS-CoV2 does no...

Figure 4. Deep highlighting illustration. The user's search term is highlighted both in the Portal results view, and in the third party pages linked from the search results.

4.5 The Pathogens Portal

While COVID-19 variants remain a significant public health risk, the focus of the international research community, as well as policy makers, is shifting to broader pandemic preparedness, as anticipated in the BY-COVID strategy. In collaboration with the EU funded VEO project (H2020 grant agreement no. 874735), we have initiated the transition of development focus from the COVID-19 Data Portal to the broader Pathogens Portal³⁰, using the codebase, experience, strategies, and established workflows where possible. On July 5, 2023, we formally released the Pathogens Portal (Figure 5). The list of pathogens featured in the portal was collated using the UK's Health and Safety Executive's list of approved biological agents³¹ and the WHO's global priority pathogens list³². It includes well-known pathogens that affect humans, including HIV, influenza, Hepatitis B, and the malaria parasite *Plasmodium falciparum*. It also covers lesser-known pathogens affecting humans, such as *Lassa mammarenavirus*, the cause of Lassa hemorrhagic fever, which can lead to deafness and even death in severe cases. The portal also contains hundreds of pathogens that affect other animals, which makes it a useful tool for food security and biodiversity, and is relevant to the One Health approach³³ to pandemic preparedness.

The Pathogens Portal currently presents nucleotide sequences, raw genomic data, sample metadata, and relevant scientific literature. We will integrate additional data types, including further molecular data types, as well as broader health and social sciences data. The Pathogens Portal provides a valuable platform for research by many pathogen-specific communities, but also an essential basis for rapid, targeted data provision in case of new potential pandemic threats as in the case of the recent global Mpox outbreak.

In addition to the European effort, the transition of national COVID-19 Data Portals to Pathogen Portals is being investigated/implemented (see "Swedish Pathogens Portal" above). A benefit of national portals is the freedom to focus on national needs, while still enabling international collaboration through the link with the European Pathogens Portal.

³⁰ Pathogens portal website: <https://www.pathogensportal.org/> [accessed 25/08/2023]

³¹ Everything in Hazard group 2 or higher from the HSE list are incorporated. The list of taxonomy names and IDs: https://github.com/enasequence/ena-content-dataflow/blob/master/classifications/pathogen_taxa/Priority_pathogens_taxonomy.csv [accessed 19/09/2023]

³² WHO publication: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/WHO-EMP-IAU-2017.12> [accessed 5/09/2023]

³³ WHO - One Health: <https://www.who.int/news-room/questions-and-answers/item/one-health> [accessed 03/09/2023]

PATHOGENS
Surveillance | Identification | Investigation

About ▾ Tools ▾ News Submit data Related resources Login

Outbreak Pathogen sequences Samples Literature Cohorts Data Hubs

Pathogens Portal

Pandemic preparedness through open biodata

Outbreak →

Raw read sequences and assembled sequences of Priority Pathogens.

1,551,107 records

Sequences →

Raw read sequences, assembled sequences and analyses of Pathogens.

16,239,177 records

Latest news →

Webinar recording: The Pathogens Portal: A gateway to vast biomolecular data for pathogen research →

8 Apr 2024

27 Mar 2024
[New paper presents Data Hubs functionality for analysing pathogen sequences](#)

19 Jan 2024
[User Forum provides useful feedback for further improvements on the Pathogens Portal](#)

23 Nov 2023
[Extending the network of infectious disease data portals: developments in Sweden and The Netherlands](#)

5 Jul 2023
[Pathogens Portal: The next steps](#)

Samples →

Pathogen samples

3,282,088 records

Literature →

Search for the latest literature about Pathogens.

130,710 records

Cohorts →

The Pathogens Portal Cohort browser presents infectious disease cohort studies that have been shared at EMBL-EBI, in collaboration with University Hospital Heidelberg (UKHD).

12 records

Figure 5. Pathogens Portal home page.

4.6 Usage indicators and attribution of data submitters and workflow developers

For a new, high profile resource and the transfer of its concepts to new infectious disease challenges, it is essential to implement fine-grained usage monitoring, to prioritise future developments and provide quantitative feedback to participant resources, funders, policy-makers and the policy sphere more broadly and to attribute credit to data and workflow contributors. We have pursued this aim in the context of T3.5. As this task does not have a directly connected deliverable, we are summarising the T3.5 work in Appendix 1 of this deliverable. This covers not only standard usage metrics, but also community level

attribution and credit, particularly for contributors to large scale works, as well as highlighting mechanisms such as ORCID and RO-Crate, and ongoing work in this area in a wider context (RDA for example).

5. Results and discussion

We have added a broad range of new metadata resources to the COVID-19 Data Portal, extending its scope beyond its original biomolecular focus, to include chemical screening, large-scale population health studies, social sciences, and a large number of related resources. Building on the metadata standards work in D3.1, metadata have been integrated from their original representation in resource-specific formats, FAIRsharing, and community standard FAIR Data Points and DCAT, demonstrating the flexibility of the underlying indexing platform.

We have also established workflows for the routine update of the metadata from external sources with the CESSDA use case, and implemented the concept of “promoting” resources from resource-level indexing (Tier 3) to record-level indexing (Tier 2), for both IDTK and EU-OPENSOURCE. The “Global Search” provides an entry point for metadata discoverability across the entire spectrum of COVID-19 Data Portal domains.

Building on source code, strategies, and experience from the COVID-19 Data Portal, we have initiated the transition to general pandemic preparedness, and have developed the Pathogens Portal, released July 5, 2023.

In the reporting period, the Swedish COVID-19 Data Portal has transitioned to the Swedish Pathogens Portal, and in close collaboration with the Swedish team we have updated our connectivity with them, in both the COVID-19 Data Portal and the Pathogens Portal.

Similar to the early stages of the COVID-19 Data Portal, the Pathogens Portal is currently focussed on biomolecular, and mainly sequence data, but will evolve towards the broad domain coverage now implemented in the COVID-19 Data Portal. Due to the often fragmented nature of pathogen research, as well as ongoing discussion on equitable data access, integration of additional data sources may be as challenging as it was for COVID-19, but we are now building on strong experience both in technical terms, and from a community building perspective.

6. Next steps and sustainability

EMBL-EBI plans to maintain the COVID-19 Data Portal for at least two years beyond the end of the BY-COVID project, while developing the Pathogens Portal and transferring relevant technologies and data. At the end of this period, it is likely that the COVID-19 Data Portal role will be fully subsumed by the Pathogens Portal, and the COVID-19 Portal will be phased out.

Work towards integrating open research data from the ISIDORE³⁴ project is ongoing to prepare for efficient integration of ISIDORE data as it becomes available [4] and to align the minimum metadata requirements. Due to different project timelines there is no concrete timeline for metadata integration. However, the metadata model and recommendations from BY-COVID are considered in defining the Minimum Metadata Requirement for pandemic preparedness in ISIDORE context. These are tailored to the operational needs of the ISIDORE project in two areas: operational management, which integrates metadata concerning data quality (and data quality management), and searchability within shared platforms to enhance reusability in meta-analyses. These two focuses will be validated by the entire ISIDORE community and published in a scientific journal, acknowledging the BY-COVID project for its foundational models and recommendations, and are also integrating needs and recommendations for sustainability of data sharing provided by the EOSC-Life project [5]. Several BY-COVID partners are also involved in this publication, as well as in a second publication on Data Mobilisation efforts and methods, which incorporates ongoing work within ISIDORE, particularly in case studies. This second paper will also be published in a peer-reviewed scientific journal by the BY-COVID community.

³⁴ ISIDORE project website: <https://isidore-project.eu/> [accessed 29/08/2023]

7. Impact

Making a range of infectious disease data sources widely discoverable, accessible and interoperable is important for research and innovation, which is increasingly multidisciplinary in nature. For example, pathogen research is accelerated by the availability of data from clinical trials, biobanks, behavioural and socioeconomic studies, particularly if the data is combined with host and pathogen omics information. Multidisciplinary data is also critical for public health decision-making, where policy questions are complex and evidence from biomolecular research, clinical studies and social sciences must be taken into account.

One lesson from the COVID-19 pandemic is that data-driven decision-making needs high quality, real-time data from many research disciplines and geographic areas in an integrated format. The BY-COVID project is building on these lessons and creating solutions for COVID-19 that can be extended to other pathogens. Resources like the COVID-19 Data Portal and FAIRsharing are central to meet these goals.

The flexible, tiered metadata discovery system across different domains, metadata standards, and maturity/robustness levels of data sources, enables the linking of FAIR data and metadata on SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19, on other related viruses and diseases, and on socio-economic consequences, across research fields, from omics, clinical, and epidemiological research, to social sciences and humanities. This has the potential to accelerate infectious disease research, surveillance and outbreak investigation.

Since its launch, the COVID-19 Data Portal has been accessed by more than 100,000 users in 187 countries and geographical areas.

The strategies that were adopted, and the experience gained, in the development of the COVID-19 data portal have been integral to the establishment of Pathogens Portal³⁵, and provide a data integration framework that supports ongoing pathogen research, as well as a platform that is ready to be scaled up rapidly in the case of any future epidemic or pandemic.

³⁵ Pathogens Portal <https://www.pathogensportal.org/> [accessed 15/09/2023]

8. References

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2. Madeira F, Pearce M, Tivey ARN, Basutkar P, Lee J, Edbali O, et al. Search and sequence analysis tools services from EMBL-EBI in 2022. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2022. doi:10.1093/nar/gkac240
3. Ohmann C, Moilanen K, Kleemola M et al. ECRIN – CESSDA strategies for cross metadata mappings in selected areas between life sciences and social sciences and humanities [version 2; peer review: 1 approved, 2 approved with reservations]. *Open Res Europe* 2023, 3:180 (<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16284.2>)
4. David R, Richard AS, Connellan C, et al., (2023a). Umbrella Data Management Plans to integrate FAIR data : lessons from the ISIDORE and BY-COVID consortia for pandemic preparedness. *Data Science Journal*. IN PRESS. Preprint: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7998443>.
5. David R, Rybina A, Burel J-M, et al. (2023b). “Be sustainable”: EOSC-Life recommendations for implementation of FAIR principles in life science data handling. *The EMBO Journal*, e115008. <https://doi.org/10.15252/embj.2023115008>

Appendix 1: Usage indicators and credit attribution

Task 3.5: Usage indicators and credit attribution (M6-M36, 22PM)

EMBL-EBI, UNIMAN, UOXF, ELIXIR Hub, ALU-Freiburg, ERINHA, INFRAFRONTIER, CRG

For a new, high profile resource and the transfer of its concepts to new infectious disease challenges, it is essential to implement fine-grained usage monitoring, to prioritise future developments and provide quantitative feedback to participant resources, funders, policy-makers and the policy sphere more broadly (in particular via Task 6.3) and to attribute credit to data and workflow contributors. We will implement standard web usage metrics (sessions, distinct IP addresses, downloads, analytic tools) and resolve them to regional as well as sectoral and commercial/academic level, where possible. We will gather referrer data from partner resources including openAIRE. Beyond interactive and computational usage of the web platform, we will explore innovative usage indicators. We will mine the full text literature for use of data identifiers presented through the portal as well as identify and quantify re-use of data in subsequent studies, for example inclusion of studies in meta-studies. We will lead new community efforts in mass aggregated dataset citation using RO-Crates, building on explorative work and working with OpenAIRE.

Participants' roles: EMBL-EBI will aggregate web-based usage data, UNIMAN will coordinate citation credit attribution and aggregation strategies, UOXF will collate metrics collected via FAIRsharing (done!) (and OpenAIRE), ALU-Freiburg will integrate tool-based usage indicators from WP4, ERINHA will ensure integration with infrastructures in INFRA-2021-EMERGENCY-02 [=ISIDORE], and ELIXIR Hub will connect to WP6.

Introduction

The COVID-19 Data Portal³⁶ is a crucial resource for integration of literature, genomic, socio-economic and pre(clinical) data on the SARS-CoV-2 virus and the COVID-19 disease. As of June 2024, the portal contains ca. 15 million viral sequences and more than one million open scientific articles on this topic. This is a crucial resource with respect to tackling not only the recent pandemic, but for planning and mitigating in the event of future such occurrences³⁷. Additionally, this is also a high profile resource, at the forefront of the public view. As such, it must endeavour to recognise the diversity and diverse types of

³⁶ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/>

³⁷ <https://www.pathogensportal.org/>

contributions^{38,39}, and must implement best practice of credit and attribution to solicit comprehensive contributions, as well as demonstrate impact for those contributors.

We highlight here how we have implemented usage monitoring across the portal, as well as the different steps we have taken to credit contributions, and other promising strategies that may be implemented.

Usage Monitoring Indicators

Usage monitoring can be divided into standard web usage metrics (sessions, distinct IP addresses, downloads, analytic tools) at the level of the portal itself, expressed for example as geolocal or sectoral (eg commercial/academic), as well as access to those components referenced from the portal (datasets, workflows, etc). Table 1 shows access stats of the portal since its launch until Feb 2024, while Table 2 shows access to the more generic Pathogens portal, launched June, 2023.

year	requests	uniq hosts	bandwidth	pages
2021	1,186,697	55,026	64,193,342,412	781,033
2022	776,347	37,080	29,173,657,153	518,547
2023	399,985	24,339	23,388,730,765	248,959
2024	189,851	10,211	4,967,462,266	140,529

Table 1. BY-COVID Data Portal web usage metrics (from launch, Oct 2021 to end Feb 2024)

year	requests	uniq hosts	bandwidth	pages
2023	163,382	5,960	16,094,247,567	139,077
2024	66,029	2,500	5,248,818,515	58,554

Table 2. Pathogens Portal web usage metrics (from launch, Jun 2023 to end Feb 2024).

³⁸ <https://coara.eu/agreement/the-commitments/>

³⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/10417069>

Credit attribution

The COVID-19 Data Portal collects relevant datasets submitted to major resource centres (e.g., EMBL-EBI, CEESDA) to facilitate data integration, sharing, and analysis in coronavirus research. The mechanisms of credit and attribution are achieved by crediting the resource from which the data is integrated and linking back to the resource itself for more detailed information (Table 3).

Primary attribution

Data type	Primary source links	Attribution/credit	Example link
Viral sequence	ENA, EnSEMBL, EVA	Country	link ⁴⁰
Host sequence	EGA, GWAS		link ⁴¹
Protein	UniProt, PDBe, Pfam, EMDb		link ⁴²

Table 3. Examples of primary Credit and attribution in portal per data type.

Besides providing attribution at the level of individual data submissions, which are integrated within the portal, the other means of attribution can be termed secondary attribution, recognising individuals, teams, institutes and involvement of these within the project. There are many ways this is achieved, and we provide some examples in the following section.

Claiming Credit

ORCID

A key method for credit attribution is the claiming of scientific artefacts to a researchers' ORCID record. Normally, this would be done in collaboration between the contributor of a dataset and the resource where the dataset is deposited. However, due to community requests, the COVID-19 implemented a pilot for direct claiming of data contributions within the portal.

⁴⁰<https://www.covid19dataportal.org/search/sequences?crossReferencesOption=all&overrideDefaultDomain=true&query=Severe%20acute%20respiratory%20syndrome%202>

⁴¹<https://www.covid19dataportal.org/search/host-sequences?crossReferencesOption=all&overrideDefaultDomain=true>

⁴²<https://www.covid19dataportal.org/search/proteins?crossReferencesOption=all&overrideDefaultDomain=true&query=Severe%20acute%20respiratory%20syndrome%202>

For viral sequences, it is possible to select relevant datasets within the portal, and then interactively claim these to a researchers' ORCID profile, building on claiming infrastructure originally implemented at EMBL-EBI in the EU-funded THOR project. See figure 1 for interface details.

Viral sequences
Raw and assembled sequence and analysis of SARS-CoV-2 and other coronaviruses

Search **Search**

Examples: lineage:B.1.1.7 , who:omicron , Severe acute respiratory syndrome 2 ...Advanced search

We have launched a drag-and-drop data submission tool, suitable for small scale viral sequence submissions. Please register your interest [here](#).

Showing 15 of 8,844,717 in All > Viral sequences > Sequences powered by

Data types: < ●●●●●●●● > [Edit table view](#)

All

- Viral sequences (21,756,560)
- Sequences (8,844,717)
- Representative sequences (224)
- Raw reads (7,192,311)
- Systematic Analyses (5,590,697)
- Studies (1,639)
- Genes (22)

<input type="checkbox"/>	Accession	Lineage	Cross-references	Collection date	Cour
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OW541498	BA.1.15.1 <input type="button" value="Omicron"/>	Viral sequences > Studies (1)	Jan 13, 2022	Germ
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OX611620	B.1.617.2 <input type="button" value="Delta"/>	Viral sequences > Studies (1)	Aug 22, 2021	Unite
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OW546943	AY.43 <input type="button" value="Delta"/>	Viral sequences > Studies (1)	Nov 17, 2021	Denrr
<input type="checkbox"/>	OX512029	BA.1.17.2 <input type="button" value="Omicron"/>	Viral sequences > Studies (1)	Jan 18, 2022	Unite
<input type="checkbox"/>	OW483799	BA.2 <input type="button" value="Omicron"/>	Viral sequences > Studies (1)	Mar 21, 2022	Unite

Figure 1: After selecting relevant records, a data contributor can click on “Claim to ORCID” to link to the ORCID authentication interface, and then connect the selected data objects to their ORCID profile.

Project level attribution

BY-COVID community standards: FAIRsharing

FAIRsharing is a registry that documents the standards, formats and terminologies used by individual resources, providing an easy way to navigate this interconnected ecosystem. It provides a ‘collection’ for BY-COVID⁴³, listing all standards and databases that are developed by BY-COVID Consortium members, as well as those standards these data resources implement. The 72 records in this collection, of which 52 are ‘standards’, can be shown as a graph⁴⁴ to show the relationships between standards used, and data resources that leverage those. Furthermore, those standards used in the project are heavily used in the wider scientific domain (an average of 26 databases use each of the standards implemented in BY-COVID project collection).

⁴³ <https://fairsharing.org/3773>

⁴⁴ <https://fairsharing.org/graph/3773>

BY-COVID community reporting: Zenodo

A specific Zenodo community⁴⁵ was created for the BY-COVID project, in an attempt to share important materials, providing a framework for making data from other infectious diseases open and accessible to everyone, as well as to share recommendations, guidance and all project deliverables from this community. This also enables some lightweight metrics capture from this resource, which displays ‘views’ and ‘downloads’.

The publications in this community are cross-referenced with a record⁴⁶ maintained at the ELIXIR Hub, which is supplemented with searches for EPMC and Grant award identifiers by text mining, and the EU maintained list (participant portal) to ensure the project record is up to date.

BY-COVID community workflows and tools

Computational workflows and tools are an important part of many research or analytic pipelines, and their creation and sharing is important to credit. In this field, there are many specific workflow systems, and registries such as WorkflowHub, a system and format agnostic workflow registry are crucial, as are well established systems such as Galaxy.

WorkflowHub

Within WorkflowHub, there is a multi-level attribution and credit system in place to enable the crediting of teams, individuals, institutes, projects, and country. For instance, a collection⁴⁷ (BY-COVID Baseline Use case) is a convenient way to capture workflows created by ‘teams’ for particular tasks or projects, and captures metadata around Funding code, public web page (study protocol) and organism, as well as authors, their institutes and ORCIDs. Additionally, a BY-COVID ‘space’⁴⁸ provides information on potentially more diverse sets of information relating to this project, though this feature is not extensively used at this time. To facilitate the use of this resource by partners, a BY-COVID guide⁴⁹ for WorkflowHub was produced. Many such guides for targeted project onboarding have been created to date, including a generalised guide, all of which are registered in workflowHub as ‘SOPs’⁵⁰ (Standard Operating Procedures’.

The COVID-19 Data Portal is importing the metadata for relevant WorkflowHub entries, crediting both the WorkflowHub as the source, and individual workflow contributors by their name (fig 2).

⁴⁵ <https://zenodo.org/communities/bycovid/>

⁴⁶ https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1yBhfpsz6gGxSPOW0h2BTRVsNxa0UWZ47tDKDI_Zev7Y/edit#gid=330726863

⁴⁷ <https://workflowhub.eu/projects/159#collections>

⁴⁸ <https://workflowhub.eu/projects/159#programmes>

⁴⁹ https://docs.google.com/document/d/19hRz2louYwoAqKRGsXjyIL2p85050fYwYzpXLAUIzjo/edit?usp=drive_link

⁵⁰ <https://workflowhub.eu/sops>

Workflows
Research workflows related to COVID-19

Search **Search**
Examples: Cheminformatics ... [Advanced search](#)

Showing 15 of 44 in All > Workflows > WorkflowHub powered by WorkflowHub **A**

Data types ◀ ● ● ● ▶ [Edit table view](#)

All
Workflows (44)
WorkflowHub (44)

License

MIT (27)
 Apache-2.0 (13)
 CC-BY-4.0 (2)

Author **B**

Björn Grüning (15)
 Dannon Baker (8)
 Delphine Larivière (8)
[More... >](#)

ID	Name	
301	Research Object Crate for V-pipe (main multi-virus version)	/
34	Research Object Crate for Genomic variants - SNPs and INDELS detection using SAMTools.	/
37	Research Object Crate for Assembly using Tophat2 and annotation (alternate)	/
39	Research Object Crate for StringTie assembly and annotation	/
417	Research Object Crate for CoVigator pipeline: variant detection pipeline for Sars-CoV-2 (and other viruses...)	†
518	Research Object Crate for VVV2_align_PE	©
519	Research Object Crate for SARS-CoV-2 Illumina Amplicon pipeline - SANBI - v1.2	†
763	Research Object Crate for coronavirushelicase_proteindrugcomplex	©
38	Research Object Crate for Unicycler assembly and annotation	/

Figure 2: Representation of workflows from WorkflowHub in the COVID-19 Data Portal, including crediting WorkflowHub as the source (label A), and individual contributors (label B).

Galaxy

The European Galaxy instance⁵¹ provides a dashboard⁵² representing tool executions; over 400,000 workflow executions and over 100,000 workflows. Since the user base of Galaxy typically access and modify registered tools regularly, it is almost impossible to track downstream modifications of natively registered ‘workflows’, especially as related to Project contexts. While it is not possible to see specifically which tools are run specifically for BY-COVID, stats for individual tools can be accessed⁵³, for ‘known tools’. But as stated, this may not reflect downstream use of those components created in the BY-COVID context. It is possible however to access stats relating to energy efficiency of tools, where they can be executed on different resources/platforms. Also, it may be possible to track tool usage where BY-COVID workflows are executed through WorkFlowHub.

⁵¹ <https://usegalaxy.eu/>

⁵² <https://stats.galaxyproject.eu/d/G09PBrEVz/by-covid?orgId=1>

⁵³ https://stats.galaxyproject.eu/d/6rsDAVfSk/tool-usage-stats-copy?orgId=1&var-tool_id=rna_star

Funder context

To ensure the strategies implemented within BY-COVID around credit and attribution addressed the perceived needs of funders, we have involved WP6 (Interoperability) at all stages of development.

Policy-makers put a lot of value on usage data of the bioinformatics resources (e.g. portals, databases, software) which they fund and/or endorse. Generally-speaking, usage data is considered good evidence of usefulness of funded work. This data does not need to be scientifically-accurate for consumption in the policy sphere (approximate numbers with documented caveats are fine). While temporal trends are very appreciated by policy-makers, aggregated or cumulative figures also suffice, particularly where temporal trends show increasing usage. Types of usage statistics that are hard to collect but are of interest funders/policy-makers include:

- User profession (researchers? clinicians? Public health official?)
- Regional locations of users (Country, regions of the world, etc)
- User context (Academia, industry)
- How data is used

An online dynamic dashboard to collate such information is generally viewed as useful, though these take significant effort to design and build, and also need long-term maintenance, since they may be fragile or require manual steps for support.

Possible improvements

While the portal provides attribution metadata in the web interface, this is not directly available through the API⁵⁴ for download; the commonly used JSON and XML formats are not available, for example here⁵⁵. One possibility would be to add RO-Crate, allowing exposure of terms such as ‘submitter’ using schema.org, and make these credit and attribution components more machine-accessible.

At the level of individual contributions, credit could be reflected using fine grained Contributor Roles from the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRedit)⁵⁶. These could even be included in the TSV format downloads as text (example⁵⁷), retrospectively using ORCID (example⁵⁸), or separately with annotations (e.g. RO-Crate⁵⁹).

⁵⁴ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/api-documentation>

⁵⁵ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/search/proteins?crossReferencesOption=all>

⁵⁶ <https://credit.niso.org/>

⁵⁷ <https://www.researchobject.org/2021-packaging-research-artefacts-with-ro-crate/manuscript.html#contributions>

⁵⁸ <https://info.orcid.org/credit-for-research-contribution/>

⁵⁹ <https://www.researchobject.org/2021-packaging-research-artefacts-with-ro-crate/ro-crate-preview.html#%23role-0000-0002-2036-8350>

The intricacies of the BY-COVID data, and the sheer number of datasets, of different types, and involving numerous contributors fits well into a specific use case for the emerging Complex citation Working Group⁶⁰ in the RDA. Earlier meetings proposed the use of RO-Crates to manage these complex data sets^{61,62}. This group was largely inactive over the past year, but UNIMAN is involved in this work now that it has restarted.

For a more precise impact assessment at the level of individual datasets, we are piloting statistics on “click-throughs”, counting the number of times a user in the COVID-19 Data Portal clicks on a specific metadata record, to access the underlying data in a contributor’s resource.

⁶⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/complex-citations-working-group>

⁶¹ <https://data.agu.org/DataCitationCoP/>

⁶² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4916734>